

**MINISTERIAL DECLARATION OF THE
SIXTH
TRILATERAL GOVERNMENTAL CONFERENCE
ON THE PROTECTION OF THE WADDEN SEA
ESBJERG, NOVEMBER 13, 1991**

MINISTER OF THE ENVIRONMENT OF THE KINGDOM OF DENMARK

**MINISTER FOR THE ENVIRONMENT, NATURE CONSERVATION AND NUCLEAR SAFETY OF THE
FEDERAL REPUBLIC OF GERMANY**

**STATE-SECRETARY OF THE MINISTRY OF AGRICULTURE, NATURE MANAGEMENT AND
FISHERIES OF THE KINGDOM OF THE NETHERLANDS**

responsible for the protection and conservation of the **Wadden Sea**

participated in the

**SIXTH TRILATERAL GOVERNMENTAL CONFERENCE ON THE PROTECTION OF THE WADDEN
SEA, ESBJERG, DENMARK, NOVEMBER 13, 1991.**

Representatives of the

- **Commission of the European Community**
- **Convention on Wetlands of International Importance especially as Waterfowl
Habitat (Ramsar Convention)**
- **English Nature, the Nature Conservancy Council for England**
- **USSR, Ministry for Nature Management and Environment Protection**

attended the Conference as observers.

PREAMBLE

The Wadden Sea extends over parts of the territories of the Netherlands, the Federal Republic of Germany and Denmark. The three countries cooperate to protect and conserve the Wadden Sea as an ecological entity, on the basis of the [Joint Declaration on the Protection of the Wadden Sea](#), which was signed in 1982 at the Third Trilateral Governmental Conference. The trilateral Wadden Sea cooperation has developed into a close cooperation involving all levels of government and is supported by a permanent common secretariat. Trilateral Governmental Conferences on the Protection of the Wadden Sea are normally held every three years.

During the last decade the Wadden Sea has been protected through a series of national initiatives so that now a chain of nature reserves, protected areas and national parks exists from Den Helder in the Netherlands, along the German North Sea Coast and the islands to Esbjerg in Denmark. In addition, the Wadden Sea has been included in the List of Wetlands of International Importance.

The participants:

- note that progress has been made to protect the Wadden Sea on a national as well as on an international basis;
- remain fully committed to implement the decisions of the 5th Governmental Conference and will continue

their efforts intensively;

- note that the importance of the Wadden Sea for the North Sea has been recognized at the North Sea Conferences, and remain committed to implement fully the decisions of these conferences without delay. Further, they will continue to give high priority to the implementation of the measures which have a special significance for the Wadden Sea, as contained in Annex 4 of the Ministerial Declaration of the Third North Sea Conference;

- welcome the decisions of the North Sea Conferences to further reduce the inputs of hazardous substances and nutrients entering the North Sea via direct inputs, rivers and the atmosphere, and to phase out PCBs and hazardous PCB-substitutes;

- underline the importance of the 1993 working group meeting at the ministerial level on the Protection of the North Sea which, amongst others, will address problems encountered with the implementation of the Ministerial Declaration of the Third North Sea Conference with regard to shipping, nutrients and pesticides;

- conscious that the Wadden Sea is an area where people live, work and recreate and note that there is therefore a need for a common strategy concerning human use within the area;

- note that within the framework of the Ramsar Convention, contracting parties are making progress with respect to the conservation of wetlands and their wise use and that the Wadden Sea is becoming a model for the cooperation of contracting parties on shared wetlands.

The participants further:

- welcome the growing interest in the Wadden Sea of governmental and inter-governmental organizations and of states which do not border the region, in particular the Commission of the European Community, the Ramsar Convention and English Nature;

- appreciate the continuous efforts of non-governmental organizations in the field of protection and conservation within the Wadden Sea and have taken notice of their recommendations to the conference;

- underline the importance of the Working Conferences on Nature Management of the Wadden Sea, in particular the Working Conferences on salt marshes (1988), dunes (1991) and wardening (1991), and the 7th International Scientific Wadden Sea Symposium (1990), and welcome the recommendations of these Conferences as useful contributions to the protection of the Wadden Sea.

The 5th Trilateral Governmental Conference on the Protection of the Wadden Sea in 1988, called for the development of common approaches to a conservation policy based upon the wise use concept. According to the definition of wise use, as formulated by the contracting parties to the Ramsar Convention, the natural potentials of the ecosystem must be maintained for present and future generations. A common Wadden Sea conservation policy based upon the wise use concept must therefore define the natural potentials of the Wadden Sea ecosystem and maintain these potentials.

The World Commission on Environment and Development - the Brundtland Commission - calls for a transition to a sustainable development by the year 2000. The participants acknowledge that they have a global responsibility to protect the Wadden Sea and its natural properties for present and future generations and they are committed to achieving such a sustainable development.

The assessment of the current state of the Wadden Sea leads to the conclusion that, although considerable progress in the field of nature and environmental protection both on a national as well as on an international level has been made, the quality of the ecosystem needs to be significantly improved in order to restore and maintain its natural potentials.

The participants considered the progress made in the implementation of the obligations ensuing from the legal instruments mentioned in the Joint Declaration on the Protection of the Wadden Sea

in 1982. They:

- note that an important part of these obligations has been implemented;
- accept that in order to achieve further progress in protecting the Wadden Sea as an ecological entity, it is necessary to further specify the basis of the trilateral cooperation, define the common objectives and direct these into common principles of approach and action.

The participants therefore decided to adopt the following **common guiding principles and objectives**:

COMMON PRINCIPLES

1 The guiding principle of the trilateral Wadden Sea policy is to achieve, as far as possible, a natural and sustainable ecosystem in which natural processes proceed in an undisturbed way.

2 This principle aims at

- (I) maintaining the water movements and the attendant geomorphological and pedological processes;
- (ii) improving the quality of water, sediment and air to levels that are not harmful for the ecosystem;
- (iii) safeguarding and optimizing the conditions for flora and fauna including
 - preservation of the Wadden Sea as a nursery area for North Sea fish;
 - conservation of the feeding, breeding, moulting and roosting areas of birds, and the birth and resting areas of seals as well as the prevention of disturbance in these areas;
 - conservation of the salt marshes and dunes;
- (iv) maintaining the scenic qualities of the landscape, in particular the variety of landscape types and the specific features of the wide, open scenery including the perception of nature and landscape.

3 The common policies as laid down in the **Joint Declaration on the Protection of the Wadden Sea from 1982**, will be further implemented based on:

- (i) the **Principle of Careful Decision Making**, i.e. to take decisions on the basis of the best available information;
- (ii) the **Principle of Avoidance**, i.e. activities which are potentially damaging to the Wadden Sea should be avoided;
- (iii) the **Precautionary Principle**, i.e. to take action to avoid activities which are assumed to have significant damaging impact on the environment, even where there is no sufficient scientific evidence to prove a causal link between activities and their impact;
- (iv) the **Principle of Translocation**, i.e. to translocate activities which are harmful to the Wadden Sea environment to areas where they will cause less environmental impact;
- (v) the **Principle of Compensation**, i.e. that the harmful effect of activities which cannot be avoided, must be balanced by compensatory measures; in those parts of the Wadden Sea where the Principle has not yet been implemented compensatory measures will be aimed for;
- (vi) the **Principle of Restoration**, i.e. that, where possible, parts of the Wadden Sea should be restored if it can be demonstrated by reference studies that the actual situation is not optimal, and that the original state is likely to be re established;
- (vii) the **Principles of Best Available Technology and Best Environmental Practice**, as defined by the Paris Commission.

4 The participants agree to address a set of common ecological targets and a comprehensive set of measures to achieve these targets at the 7th Trilateral Governmental Conference.

5 The participants agree to undertake the necessary steps to establish a coherent special conservation area covered by a coordinated management plan for the Wadden Sea, stretching from Esbjerg to Den Helder, taking into account especially the requirements of the EC Bird Directive 79/409/EC, the forthcoming Habitat Directive and the Ramsar Convention.

[Top of page](#)

COMMON OBJECTIVES

The participants underline that the main aim of the trilateral cooperation is the protection of the Wadden Sea as a nature area. The participants are conscious that the Wadden Sea area is an area where people live, work and recreate and that in this respect there is a need for a common strategy for the human use of the area, based upon the above principles.

They therefore agree:

SEA DEFENCE, SALT MARSH MANAGEMENT AND DUNE PROTECTION

6 To further harmonize the interests of nature protection and sea defence measures, taking into account that the safety of the inhabitants is essential and to this end

6.1 to prohibit, in principle, embankment and to minimize unavoidable loss of biotopes by sea defence measures;

6.2 to adequately protect salt marshes and dunes in order to allow natural processes to take place within these habitats, with special emphasis on flora and fauna;

6.3 to aim for the restoration of salt marshes by opening summer dikes, provided that it fits into the ecological target of the region;

6.4 to apply best environmental practice in salt marsh and dune protection and development;

6.5 to stop the application of fertilizers and pesticides and other toxic substances on the salt marshes.

HARBOR AND INDUSTRIAL FACILITIES

7 To avoid new, not yet approved plans for the extension or major modifications of harbor and industrial facilities immediately adjacent to the Wadden Sea. In principle such measures should only be allowed to take place at inland sites and under strict environmental conditions according to applicable law.

SHIPPING

8 To increase their efforts towards the elimination of operational pollution and the minimization of accidental discharges by

8.1 the establishment of a system to provide information concerning vessels carrying hazardous substances;

8.2 reducing the incineration of ships operational garbage and enforcing disposal on the shore;

8.3 making available adequate facilities for the reception of harmful wastes and garbage from ships in the Wadden Sea ports at reasonable costs or without charging the individual ship, ensuring that the best environmental objectives are met and that high standards of service are performed;

8.4 imposing speed limits within the Wadden Sea where such are deemed necessary by the authorities responsible, taking safety and environmental factors into account;

8.5 prohibiting hovercraft within the Wadden Sea; this item will be discussed again at the next Wadden Sea Governmental Conference;

8.6 welcoming the initiative of the Netherlands within the IMO, which aims at adequate measures to minimize the detrimental effects of lipophilic substances as soon as possible, recognizing the harmful effects these substances have on sea- and coastal birds.

DREDGING ACTIVITIES

9 To welcome the "Guidelines for the Management of dredged material", which have been adopted by the Oslo Commission in its meeting in June 1991 and to fully implement these guidelines in the Wadden Sea and to this end

9.1 to cooperate in developing national criteria with regard to dredging operations and disposal of dredged material in accordance with these guidelines;

9.2 to consider the need to harmonize these sets of criteria if differences based on natural variations in sediment quality arise.

ENERGY RESOURCES

Exploration and exploitation of oil and gas

10 To limit those offshore activities that have an adverse impact on the Wadden Sea environment and to this end

10.1 to aim at avoiding the construction of new installations until 1994 and to allow for exemptions only where energy supply interests prevail over adverse environmental impacts; with regard to existing rights and concessions the participants will strive and appeal energetically to the companies to refrain from exerting these rights (moratorium);

10.2 to evaluate this approach at the next Governmental Wadden Sea Conference;

10.3 to apply zero-discharges immediately or at the latest whenever existing exploration and exploitation rights are to be renewed;

10.4 to make the exploration and exploitation of energy resources in the adjacent areas of the North Sea up to 12 nautical miles offshore in principle subject to zero-discharges into the sea of oil contaminated cuttings and to use the best practicable means of cleaning of other contaminated cuttings and substances;

10.5 to avoid in principle the construction of new pipelines and the planning of new location lines, unless already approved, and to allow exemptions only if they can be justified by considerable environmental and energy supply interests in consideration of the common good;

10.6 to only carry out seismic investigations in the Wadden Sea using the best available methods and at such times so as to ensure a minimal disturbance of fish, birds and seals.

Wind energy

11 To acknowledge the basically positive contribution of wind energy with regard to the environment and nature conservation, and also acknowledge the conservation of birds and the scenic quality of the landscape when generating wind energy and to this end

11.1 to prohibit the construction of wind turbines in the Wadden Sea seaward of the seawalls and the

coastline;

11.2 to take into particular consideration the maintenance and protection of the Wadden Sea's overall character regarding ecology and scenic quality, in the framework of individual assessments, when wind energy installations are constructed on the islands and in a zone adjacent to the Wadden Sea.

EXTRACTION OF SAND AND CLAY

12 To minimize the impact of the extraction of sand and clay in the Wadden Sea in order to meet the aims of undisturbed sedimentation processes, and to this end

12.1 to limit the extraction of sand to the dredging and maintenance of shipping lanes or for sea defence purposes, preferably combining these two activities, or to take measures aiming at such a situation in considerable parts of the Wadden Sea;

12.2 to only use sand from the North Sea for the supplementation of sand lost from the coasts of the barrier islands;

12.3 to allow the small scale extraction of clay for sea-defence measures in cases of urgent and sudden need only in cases where no other deposits are available behind the dikes.

FISHERIES

Cockle fishery

13 To be aware of the negative ecological effects caused by the cockle fishery, that cockle fishery will be ended in the German part of the Wadden Sea by 01.03.92, and that cockle fishery in Denmark will only be carried out in quite specific, well-defined areas.

14 To limit or reduce the negative ecological effects of cockle fishery in the Dutch part of the Wadden Sea by

14.1 closing permanently considerable parts including intertidal and subtidal areas;

14.2 taking appropriate technical and management measures.

Mussel fishery

15 To limit the negative ecological impact of mussel fishery on the Wadden Sea environment and to this end

15.1 to close considerable parts of the Wadden Sea, including intertidal and subtidal areas.

Fin-fish fisheries

16 To express concern about the incidental bycatch of marine mammals in fishing gears, and to investigate possibilities for technical improvements to minimize this threat to wildlife in the Wadden Sea.

RECREATION

17 To maintain the recreational values of the Wadden Sea area and to this end

17.1 to establish zones covering the most sensitive areas where no recreational activities including excursion ships and recreational boating is allowed;

17.2 to concentrate recreation pressure by allowing ships to stay only within 200 m of the nearest channel at low water;

17.3 to impose a speed limit on recreational boats outside the designated shipping routes;

17.4 to prohibit the use of hovercraft and jet scooters;

17.5 to limit the use of jet skis, water skis and similar motorized equipment to small designated areas;

17.6 to avoid new marinas and to allow extension of the existing marina capacity only within the approved levels.

HUNTING

18 To reduce the disturbance to wildlife caused by hunting in the Wadden Sea area, and to this end

18.1 to progressively phase out hunting of migratory species in the Wadden Sea;

18.2 to evaluate the issue at the next Governmental Conference;

18.3 to allow hunting of non-migratory species only if it can be made clear that migratory species are not harmed;

18.4 to prohibit the use of lead pellets in the Wadden Sea area by February 1993.

CIVIL AIR TRAFFIC

19 To limit the impact of civil air traffic on the Wadden Sea, and to this end

19.1 to prohibit the building of new civil airports in the Wadden Sea area;

19.2 to restrict the rebuilding and expansion of existing civil airports in the Wadden Sea area to cases where this is essential in order to increase the safety of air traffic;

19.3 to establish a minimum [flight](#) altitude of 1500 to 2000 feet (450 - 600 m) in the Wadden Sea area and to establish flight corridors in less vulnerable parts of the area, where a minimum flight altitude of 700 feet (210 m) on working days and 1000 feet (300 m) during weekends is valid;

19.4 to prohibit the use of ultra-light aircraft in the Wadden Sea area with the exception of scientific and enforcement purposes; this item will be discussed again at the next Wadden Sea Governmental Conference;

19.5 to establish helicopter flight routes and altitudes in such a way that disturbance to wildlife is minimized;

19.6 to prohibit in principle advertisement flights.

MILITARY ACTIVITIES

20 To further reduce the impact of military activities and to this end

20.1 to reduce the negative effects of low altitude flight routes of military aircraft by reducing the number of flights and reducing the maximum speed;

20.2 to examine the possibilities of concentrating and/or phasing out military activities in the Wadden Sea on the basis of a study of their environmental impacts:

(i) to concentrate shooting ranges near Den Helder, the Netherlands;

(ii) to combine activities of Noordvaarder (Terschelling) and Vliehors (Vlieland), the Netherlands;

(iii) to phase out the shooting ranges at the Meldorfer Bucht and Sylt;

20.3 to take coordinated action to minimize disturbance caused by military air traffic in the Wadden Sea area;

20.4 to give high priority to the assignment of redundant shooting ranges as nature protection areas.

INPUT OF POLLUTING SUBSTANCES

21 To welcome the decisions reached at the Third International North Sea Conference regarding the reduction of the inputs of hazardous substances and the phasing out of PCBs, and in addition agree

21.1 to achieve a significant reduction (of 50% or more) of total inputs (via all pathways) of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) and organotin compounds, between 1985 and 1995, provided the use of best available techniques makes such a reduction possible;

21.2 to take measures to phase out and to destroy in an environmentally safe manner hazardous PCB-substitutes by 1995;

21.3 to examine the possibilities of designating the catchment area of the Wadden Sea a sensitive area according to the EC Nitrate and Municipal Waste Water Directives.

CLIMATIC CHANGES AND SEA LEVEL RISE

22 To acknowledge that the possible climatic changes and sea level rise, resulting from the enhanced greenhouse effect, may result in significant changes in the ecosystem and the functions of the Wadden Sea and therefore welcome the important work of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) and the UNCED Climate Convention and support the actions mentioned in the Noordwijk Declaration on Atmospheric Pollution and Climatic Change (November 1989). Furthermore agree

22.1 to express their concern about the possible ecological damage due to the greenhouse-effect, especially the loss of biotopes or species through sea level rise or increase in water temperature;

22.2 to stress the need for research and information about the effects and risks of the expected changes, and about possible adaptive measures;

22.3 to devote one of the next working conferences or a workshop to these questions.

RESTORATION OF THE WADDEN SEA AND REINTRODUCTION OF SPECIES

23 To develop plans for restoring parts of the Wadden Sea if it can be shown by scientific research that the actual values and actual functions of the Wadden Sea are not satisfactory and if it is in accordance with the general objectives.

24 To continue the efforts to reintroduce the houting into the Wadden Sea area on a coordinated basis.

SPECIES PROTECTION

Red List Marine Species and Biotopes

25 To broaden and intensify the protection of plants and animals, and to this end agree

25.1 to develop a Red List of marine and coastal species and biotopes in the Wadden Sea area covering the three member states which points out the endangered species, both within the Wadden Sea taken as an entity and in separate areas of each Wadden Sea country;

25.2 to develop common conservation objectives for such species and biotopes and to take appropriate

action for their protection by implementing special programs if these can prevent the extinction of such animals, and by taking general measures to improve the environment as a whole.

Conservation of Seals and Small Cetaceans

26 To welcome the Conservation and Management Plan for the Wadden Sea Seal Population 1991-1995, which has been elaborated in accordance with art. 4 of the Agreement on the Conservation of Seals in the Wadden Sea.

27 To investigate which additional measures can be taken for the protection of the grey seal.

28 To welcome the Agreement on the Conservation of Small Cetaceans of the Baltic and the North Sea, and to cooperate closely with its respective bodies where appropriate.

WARDENING OF THE WADDEN SEA

29 To ensure that adequate wardening of the whole Wadden Sea will be established guided by the common standards as set out in **Annex 1**, before the next Governmental Conference.

ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT ASSESSMENT

30 To intend to harmonize environmental impact assessment (EIA) with regard to the activities in the Wadden Sea region, without prejudice to the existing national legislation, taking into account the EC Directive 85/337 concerning the Assessment of the Environmental Impact of Certain Public and Private Projects, and noting the ECE Convention on EIA (Helsinki, 1990).

31 To inform and, where necessary to consult with other Wadden Sea States, whenever an environmental impact assessment is executed for projects which might have significant adverse impact within the Wadden Sea area.

MUTUAL ASSISTANCE

32 To investigate the possibilities for the development of a system of mutual assistance and/or exchange of information in cases of major accidents or other incidents which could lead to pollution of the Wadden Sea and with regards to other problems such as epidemics.

COOPERATION IN THE FIELD OF MONITORING AND SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH

33 To cooperate in scientific research and monitoring with respect to the Wadden Sea by

33.1 elaborating a harmonized program of studies on items of special interest and in particular with respect to the common protection of the area;

33.2 welcoming the recommendations of the working group on the development of a common Wadden Sea Monitoring Program and instructing the Trilateral Working Group (TWG) to further implement the Program in accordance with the terms of reference as elaborated by the Trilateral Working Group;

33.3 designating sufficiently large areas, spread evenly over the Wadden Sea, where all exploitation and all disturbing activities are banned and which can serve as reference areas for scientific purposes;

33.4 cooperating in the evaluation and publication of the results of all international waterfowl counts since 1980 for the entire Wadden Sea on a coordinated basis according to a joint project, within the resources available.

COOPERATION IN THE FIELD OF PUBLIC INFORMATION

34 To cooperate within the realms of public information work with the aim of increasing the awareness of

the general public to the problems facing the Wadden Sea environment as a whole and in order to investigate the possibilities

34.1 of establishing a cooperation between the main public information and education centers of the Wadden Sea area;

34.2 of exchanging exhibitions and other adequate information between the centers.

COOPERATION WITH RESPECT TO INTERNATIONAL FORA

World Heritage Convention

35 To acknowledge that the Wadden Sea would benefit from inclusion in the World Heritage List of the Convention for the Protection of the Cultural and Natural Heritage (1972), as is stated in the report on the potential designation of the Wadden Sea as a World Heritage Site and to this end to develop a joint proposal for the nomination of the Wadden Sea in the World Heritage List.

Ramsar Convention

36 To continue to support the activities of the Convention on Wetlands of International Importance Especially as Waterfowl Habitat (Ramsar Convention, 1971) in particular with respect to the wise use issue and the cooperation on the protection of shared wetlands.

37 To examine whether it is possible in terms of ecological values to delimitate the Wadden Sea region on a common basis according to Article 2.1 of the Ramsar Convention.

38 To investigate whether zoning can be used to improve the protection of the Wadden Sea with respect to:

- (i) the designation of buffer areas adjacent to the Wadden Sea area (both landward and seaward) in order to enable a better regulation of activities outside the Wadden Sea which could have an impact on the Wadden Sea ecosystem;
- (ii) the need to harmonize zoning measures within the Wadden Sea, including the designation of special protection zones.

Flyway Co-operation

39 To recognize that the Ramsar Convention Conference, 1990, and the Western Palearctic Waterfowl Agreement currently considered in the framework of the Bonn Convention, call for the establishment of partnerships between wetlands and parties to protect waterfowl and wetlands.

40 To acknowledge that the Wadden Sea is a core area for the migrating waterfowl of the East Atlantic Flyway and to this end agree on the necessity for a common approach with regard to the protection of migrating waterfowl in the whole range of the flyway and further agree to carry out a feasibility study into monitoring and cooperation, acknowledging the existing and ongoing bilateral cooperation between the USSR and Germany and the USSR and the Netherlands.

European Community

41 To work towards integrating the protection of the Wadden Sea into the environmental policies of the European Communities by

41.1 examining the developments of the internal market in relation to the protection of the Wadden Sea;

41.2 promoting the designation of the Wadden Sea as a special conservation area according to Annex 1 of the draft EC Directive on the Protection of Natural and Semi-natural Habitats and of Wild Fauna and Flora, when this comes into force;

41.3 examining the possibilities of cooperation on the national and regional level supported by the EC, to enable a more comprehensive protection of the Wadden Sea.

North Sea Conferences

42 To take notice of the invitation of the Third International North Sea Conference to continue to report on the progress made with respect to the protection of the Wadden Sea to the International North Sea Conferences and to this end agree

42.1 to develop recommendations for further measures to the Fourth International North Sea Conference in 1995 at the Seventh Trilateral Governmental Conference on the Protection of the Wadden Sea (1994);

42.2 when assessing the need for such recommendations that special attention will be paid to:

- (i) the reduction of nutrients and other pollutants reaching the Wadden Sea; and
- (ii) the protection of other coastal, estuarine and open sea areas (e.g. The Wash) which are also visited by bird populations which use the Wadden Sea and which have strong similar interests with regard to species and populations.

The Wash

43 To welcome the Memorandum of Intent between the Trilateral Wadden Sea Cooperation and the English Nature on the Wash / North Norfolk Coast and the Wadden Sea.

ARRANGEMENTS FOR THE FUTURE COOPERATION

With regard to future work, the participants made the following arrangements:

The Netherlands will chair the Trilateral Cooperation on the Protection of the Wadden Sea from January 1st, 1992.

The 7th Trilateral Governmental Conference on the Protection of the Wadden Sea will be held in 1994 at the invitation of the Government of the Netherlands.

This conference will address, inter alia:

- a. the progress made in implementation of the Joint Declaration on the Protection of the Wadden Sea;
- b. the progress made in implementation of the common principles, objectives and actions arising from the Declaration of the 6th Trilateral Governmental Conference on the Protection of the Wadden Sea;
- c. the state of the Wadden Sea as stated in the Quality Status Report of the Wadden Sea which will be finalized in 1993 as a regional report of the overall North Sea Quality Status Report;
- d. the need for further measures based upon the assessment of the progress made and of the state of the Wadden Sea.

The 8th International Scientific Wadden Sea Symposium will be held in 1992 and hosted by Denmark.

For the Government of the
Kingdom of Denmark
Mr. P. Stig Møller

For the Government of the
Federal Republic of Germany
Prof. Dr. K. Töpfer

For the Government of the
Kingdom of The Netherlands
Mr. J. D. Gabor

[Top of page](#)

ANNEX 1

COMMON STANDARDS FOR THE WARDENING OF THE WADDEN SEA

1. To ensure the adequate wardening of the whole Wadden Sea the following standards should be implemented:

- a. some wardens should be employed, on a full time basis, by the state nature conservation authorities;
- b. their duties should be to:
 - ensure that the area under their supervision is adequately protected and to monitor possible environmental changes within its borders;
 - maintain contact with local authorities and user-groups;
 - disseminate information to the general public;
 - ensure the implementation of the provisions of the nature conservation laws; and
 - give a substantial annual report on the area under their supervision;
- c. they should be issued with sufficient authority and state employed wardens should have executive power.

2. In addition to the state employed wardens a number of voluntary wardens should be appointed.

3. Each national park, nature reserve and other protected area should have an adequate number of wardens to provide continuous on-site wardening in the Wadden Sea area. They should be sufficiently well equipped with vessels, vehicles etc. to carry out their duties.

4. The wardens should be based in the local communities and should have an adequate education in order to be able to carry out their duties. Training programs should be established to maintain and improve wardening standards, personal status and skills.

5. One of the most important duties of the warden is to inform user-groups and visitors to comply with the regulations of protected areas. This includes the provision of adequate on-site information and interpretive material.

6. Wardening systems should coordinate their activities and cooperate with other authorities, e.g. fisheries, pollution control, police, coastal protection agencies, and private nature organizations to achieve efficient implementation of regulations and by-laws.

7. A coordinating committee should be established by the authority which employs the wardens in order to bring together representatives of other organizations and exchange information on a regular basis. An efficient communication network should also be established.

8. Cross-border cooperation in wardening should be promoted between countries and states in the Wadden Sea area.

9. Each area should adopt a wardening plan reviewed at regular intervals.

10. Wardening systems developed in other protected areas could be used as examples for the Wadden Sea.

11. Wardens in the Wadden Sea should be equipped with photo equipment, in order to be able to control flight altitudes and flight routes. Military monitoring of flight altitudes of jet fighters, e.g. by the Sky-Guard-System, should be intensified.